

Globalization towards Global Governance: Emerging Dynamics

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Abstract :

Globalization involves the multiplication of existing social, political and economic network. Another quality of globalization is reflected in the expansion and stretching of social relations activities and interdependencies. The inter-dependency is not merely on an objective, material level but it involves the subjective dimension as well. So, people become increasingly conscious of growing manifestation of social interdependence as it gradually changes people's individual and collective identities which impact the way they act in the world. Formation of global civil society has also been facilitated by the speed and ease of modern global communications. It is the result of the growing awareness of common interests between groups in different countries and regions of the World. Although there are considerable inequalities between the agencies of transnational civil society in terms of resources influence and access to key centers of global decision making.

Keywords : Global society, social interdependence, IGO's, Trans-governmental, Global parliament, Transnational agencies, Green peace global economy.

Globalization is the process of increasing interconnectedness between societies in such a way that events in one part of the World have more and more

effects on the people and societies far away. In a globalize World political economic, cultural and social events become more and more interconnected. In other words, societies are affected more and more extensively and more and more deeply by events of other societies. World wide television communications, global newspapers, international social movements such as Amnesty international or Greenpeace global economy are examples of the increased interconnectedness due to globalization. (Steger, 2009)

Globalization refers to a multidimensional set of social processes that create, multiply, stretch and intensify worldwide social interdependence and exchanges. Anthony Giddens (Giddens, 1964) has defined globalization as the intensification of worldwide social relations which link distant locations in such a way that local happenings are shaped by events occurring many miles away and vice versa.

Globalization involves the creation of new and the multiplication of existing social networks and activities that increasingly over come traditional political economic, cultural and geographical boundaries. Another quality of globalization is reflected in the expansion and stretching of social relations activities and interdependencies. For example today financial markets are stretched around the globe and shopping malls have commodities from all the Regions of the World. It has intensified and accelerated social exchanges and activities. Through internet and satellites people get information in seconds.

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The Political Dimension of Globalization :

Political dimension of globalization refers to the intensification and expansion of political interrelations across the globe. Political globalization has resulted in the rise of supraterritorial institutions and associations which have common norms and interests. Political Globalization refers to an increasing trend towards multilaterals (in which the United Nations plays a key and toward an emerging

transnational state apparatus and toward the emergence of national and international non-governmental organizations that act as watch dogs over governments and have increased their activities and influence (Moghadam, 2005). Under conditions of Political Globalization states are increasingly embedded in overlapping worldwide webs of multilateral institutions and multilateral politics such as NATO and the World Bank. This event of Global Governance compasses the multitude of formal and informal, structures of political coordination among governments, inter-governmental and transnational agencies which have common purposes or collectively agreed goals (Anthony McGrew, 2007).

Political Globalization and Global Governance :

Political globalization has given way to global governance. There has been a remarkable growth in interrelated power centers such as municipal and provincial authorities, regional blocs, international organizations and national and international private sector associations.

On the municipal and provincial level, there has a remarkable growth in the common policy initiatives and trans-border links between various sub state authorities. For example Chinese provinces and US, federal states have established permanent missions and points of contact together. Another example of international cooperation on the municipal level is the rise of powerful city networks like the World association of major metropolis that deals with common local issues across national borders. Global cities like Tokyo, London, New York and Singapore tend to be more closely connected to each other than to many cities in their own country. (Steger, 2009)

On the regional level, there has been an extra ordinary proliferation of multi-lateral organizations and agreements. Regional blocs have evolved into loose political rations with common institution of governance. For example, EU, AU, ARF, and MERCOSUR, etc. Some observers speculate that these organizations will eventually replace nation states as the basic unit of governance due to their growing importance. (Ibid)

On a global level, governments have formed a number of international organizations like UN, NATO, WTO and OECD, etc. Membership of these organizations is

open to all the states and decision-making authority lies with the representatives from National Government. So, power in the global system is not centralized in states but it is distributed among various transnational authorities. Sovereignty of nation states is now divided and shared between local, national, regional and global authorities (Mansfred Steger, 2003). This has resulted in the evolution of global governance across the World. Global politics which involves diversity of actors and institutions is not just confine to traditional geographical concerns but also to issues of global concern like economic, environment, human rights, terrorism, drugs, etc.

An international regime has been created by IGO's (International Governmental Organization) that formulate international norms, rules, principles and decision-making procedure. IGO's are institutions created and joined by State Governments which gave them authority to make collective decisions on common problems. The most prominent of all is the UN. IGO's are affecting the policies of Politicians and Bureaucrats of a state. The Global Governance formed by these IGO's has created "trans-governmental collision of bureaucrats." (Keohane and Nye cited in McGrew, 1992)

Hyperglobalizers argue that the question of responsibility and accountability is associated with global governance. The worry is that most of the emerging powerful actors in a globalized. World are not accountable. It is not clear who are the transnational social movements responsible and democratically accountable.

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The emerging structure of Global Governance is also shaped by Global civil society, which refers to the vast assemblage of groups operating across borders and beyond the reach of Governments. Critics of Globalization say that Global North has a greater say in Global Governance and developing. Global South has ended their sovereignty with the dominance of America.

Some globalization researchers believe that political globalization would facilitate the emergence of a cosmopolitan democracy that would constitute the basis for a plurality of identities, having mutual toleration and accountability. According to David Held (McGrew and David Held, 1995) one of the chief exponents of this view, the cosmopolitan democracy of the future would contain the following political features :

1. A Global Parliament connected to regions, states and localities.
2. A new charter of rights and duties locked into different domains of political, social and economic power.
3. The formal separation of political and economic interest.
4. An inter-connected global legal system with mechanism of enforcements from the local to the global. (Steger, 2009)

Demise of the Nation State :

Hyperglobalizers argue that Globalization involves the decline of bounded territory and there is rise of borderless World. Political power is located in global social formations through global networks rather than through territorially based states. Nation states have already lost their dominant role in the Global economy. States are becoming less capable of determining the direction of social life within their borders. Daniel Bell (Bell, 1987) has rightly mentioned that globalization is linked with the “crises of the territorial nation state”. National boundaries no longer hold good. The internal external divides have been washed away by the high waves of the globalization. Even the territorial divisions have become so irrelevant that the Global Capital market now controls the exchange rates. The level of inter-connectedness has so much intensified due to globalization that decision taken in one state leaves its impact on others. Economic developments like trade liberalization and de-regulation have significantly constrained the independent national policies in economy.

The recent financial depression of US had impact on World economy and other national economies. Global markets frequently under mine the capacity of governments to set independent national policy objectives and impose their own domestic standards.

Hirst and Thompson (Hirst and Thompson, 1999) argue that the effect of globalization is as such that it makes National Governments powerless. Hyper-globalizers observe that nation states have lost their dominant role in decision-making due to growing power of transnational organizations. As territorial divisions are becoming increasingly irrelevant, states are now less capable of determining the direction of social life within their borders.

A group of globalization skeptics disagrees and says that governments can still take measures to make their economies more or less attractive to global investors. Nation states have re-gained control over education, infrastructure and population movements, etc. Global integration has been restricted by the immigration control and population registration and monitoring policies of the nation state. Although only 2% of the World's population live outside their country of origin still immigration control has become a central issue in the most advanced nations. Many governments seek to restrict population flows, particularly from the global south. Another example of the nation state maintaining sovereignty is related to their national security measures. In the post - 9/11 terrorist attacks nation states took drastic national security measures that restricted the people's freedom of movement and assembly across the border. These measures which were implemented worldwide reflected counter to the hyperglobalizers predictions of a borderless World (Steger, 2003).

At the same time the activities of global terrorist networks have enforced the national governments to engage in new forms of international co-operation. Contemporary globalization has weakened the traditional functions of the nation state.

The Cultural Dimension of Globalization :

Cultural globalization refers to the intensification and expansion of cultural flows across the globe. Culture is a very broad concept which includes symbolic construction, articulation and dissemination of meaning. The volume and extent of cultural transmissions in the contemporary period have exceeded the earlier eras. Due to internet and other new technologies, there is more free and wide circulation of individualism, consumption and various religious discourses. The internet is associated with the process of cultural globalization because it allows interaction and communication between people from very different life styles and from very different cultures.

There is growth of cross-cultural contacts leading towards multiculturalism. Some feel that there is rise of an increasingly homogenized popular culture which is basically western culture, across the World. So we are not moving towards cultural diversity, but there is an imposition of western culture through cultural globalization (Steger, 2003). Others consider that multi-culturalization is to promote peace and understanding between people.

The proponents of cultural homogenization argue that western norms and lifestyles are overwhelming more vulnerable cultures and spreading cultural imperialism. American sociologist George Ritzer (Ritzer, 1993) coined the term “Mc.Donalization” to describe the wide ranging socio-cultural process by which the principles of the fast food restaurant are coming to dominate more and more sectors of American society as well as the rest of the World.

Optimistic hyperglobalizers agree that cultural globalization generates more sameness. For them, this outcome is a good thing. For example, American social theorist Francis Fukuyama supports the global spread of Anglo-American values and lifestyles as he feels that the culture of democracy and free markets are also being promoted with these values. Sociologist Ronald Robertson (Robertson, 2014) contends that global cultural flows oftener invigorate local cultural riches. Hence, western consumerist forces of sameness do not dominate and local differences still play an important role in creating unique cultural constellations. He argues that instead of cultural homogenization, process of globalization is taking place which is a complex interaction of the global and local culture.

The contemporary experience of living and acting across cultural borders has two meanings- first is the loss of traditional meanings and second is the creation of new symbolic expressions. Cultural globalization has contributed to a remarkable shift in people’s consciousness. It appears that the old structures of modernity are slowly giving way to a new “post modern” framework which is characterized by a less stable sense of identity and knowledge. Cultural globalization can have different kinds of effects. In certain contexts, global cultural flows might change traditional manifestations of national identity under the impact of popular culture characterized by sameness. In other countries it might foster new expressions of cultural particularism and in some other societies it might encourage cultural hybridity. In fact, hardly any society in the World today possesses an “authentic”, self-contained culture and is affected by the global cultural flows.

The Role of the Media :

To a large extent, global cultural flows in today's time are generated and directed by global media express, who work through powerful communication technologies. During the last two decades a small group of very large Transnational-Corporations have dominated the global market for entertainment news, television and film, etc. For example, media conglomerates like AT&T, Sony, Time Warner, Disney, News Corporation have dominated the communications industry and nearly all of these corporations have been ranked among the largest 300 non-financial firms in the World. Most media analysts concede that global commercial media market has created the global oligopoly like oil and automotive industries created in the early 20th century. Recent studies have shown that people from all age groups are watching TV programs more than ever before. The values disseminated by transactional media have resulted in the cultural hegemony of the popular culture as some of the people opine. This has also led to the depoliticization of social reality and the weakening of civic bonds. (Steger, 2003)

One of the negative consequences of the transnational media is the transformation of news broadcasts and educational programmes into entertainment shows. Media firms are pursuing higher profits by having alliances between news and entertainment companies, as news is less than half as profitable as entertainment. Professional autonomy of journalism is also interfered as a result of cultural globalization.

The Globalization of Languages :

The globalization of languages can be viewed as a process by which some languages are increasingly used in international communication while others lose their prominence and even disappear due to lack of speakers. Cultural changes brought about by globalization can be measured by evaluating the shifting global patterns of languages use.

Movements of people across the World have influenced the globalization of languages. People carry their languages to different place by migration and traveling. Internet has also become a global medium for instant communication and quick access to information. Language use on the internet reflects the dominance and use of variety of languages in international communication.

Foreign language learning and tourism facilitate the spread of languages beyond national or cultural boundaries. Similarly, international scientific publications which contain the languages of global intellectual discourse also spread the globalization of languages. There is growing global significance of a few languages like English, Chinese, Spanish and French, etc. and simultaneously there is decline in the significance of other languages. Anglo-American culture is making English the global language of the 21st century. Today, more than 80% of the content posted on the internet is in English. So, cultural globalization has resulted in the globalization of languages. (Steger, 2003)

Cultural Values and Environmental Degradation :

Environmental degradation was relatively localized and occurred over thousands of years ago in ancient times. But in the last few decades the scale and speed of earth's environmental decline have been unprecedented with the advent of industrial revolution. Through globalization values and beliefs of consumerism are spreading across the World. Global population has increased at a faster rate, resulting in increased demands for food, energy resources and other things. Vastly increased demands have put severe pressure on the planet's ecosystems. Large areas of earth's surface have nearly ceased to be biologically productive. These are major manifestations and consequences of global environmental degradation in the form of patterns of consumption, global warming, trans-boundary pollution, food insecurity diseases, etc. (Max Roser, 2013)

Uncontrolled population growth presents a serious problem to the global environment. Human induced climate change such as global warming has also affected environment seriously. The rapid buildup of gas emissions, including carbon-dioxide, methane nitrous and sulfur oxides and chlorofluorocarbon in the earth's atmosphere has enhanced earth's capacity to trap heat and resulted in 'greenhouse effect', which has raised earth's temperature Worldwide. Further increase in global temperatures could lead to partial meltdowns of polar ice caps, causing rise in sea levels, etc.

Trans-boundary pollution has caused the release of vast amounts of synthetic chemicals into the air and water which has depleted earth's protective Ozone layer. Other forms of trans-boundary pollution include industrial emissions of sulfur and

nitrogen oxides. These chemicals return to the ground in the form of acid rains and damage forests, soils and freshwater ecosystems. The most ominous problem associated with globalization of environmental degradation in the contemporary era is the worldwide destruction of biodiversity. Half the Worlds' wetlands have already been destroyed and the biodiversity of freshwater ecosystem is under danger. (www.epa.gov) Although many international treaties and arrangements have been signed to control environmental degradation, but most of these treaties lack effective international enforcement mechanisms.

So, the culture of consumerism has resulted in global environmental degradation. Global cultural flows, which are facilitated by global media has impact on the globalization of languages and environmental degradation.

There are many debates about whether globalization increases or reduces cultural diversity or homogenization. For many, the influences of western culture through TV, Cinema, advertising, radio, etc. are substituting for and competing with local and minority cultures. This is increasing risk behaviors such as smoking and alcohol consumption, increasing social conflict, loss of identity, dislocation and dissatisfaction, etc. Others argue that greater cultural exchange is likely to increase tolerance and understanding and more access to information can create better life style and health benefits, such as gender equality, greater respect for human rights, etc.

Many global villages have been formed due to global communications, through which societies come close together and develop shared values and interests. Global communications play an important role in the cultural dimension of globalization. New information technologies such as internet, mobile phones, satellite TV is becoming cheaper and more widely available. This is increasing ease and speed of connectivity which has indirect influences on people. For example, global advertising campaigns may increase levels of tobacco use but on the positive side the internet democratizes access to information and makes it easier to share knowledge for health professionals. Despite advances in global communications, a massive 'information gap' remains between developed and developing countries. Over 70% of Africans will not make a telephone call in their lifetime, nor use the internet. Ownership and influence over the content of communication is important. So, integration of global markets and communication channels lead to a much high level of interaction.

Despite of much advancement towards formation of whole world as global village, there is an existence of massive gap between developed and developing countries. Bridging inequalities between nations will be a major challenge faced by people in favour of global political society.

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